

SHORT NOTES

Apparent Molal Volumes of KCl and NaCl Solutions in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 40°

N. C. Das, H. Mohapatra, and P. B. Das

Apparent molal volumes (Φ) of KCl and NaCl solutions in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures by weight have been studied at 40°. This study has been undertaken as a part of a programme to investigate the effect of solvent composition on the diameter of the ion pair (to be published later).

Apparent molal volumes of KCl and NaCl solutions have been calculated from the density data of Das and Das¹ by using the equation:

$$\Phi = \frac{M}{\rho_0} - \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\rho_0} \right) \frac{10^3}{C}$$

where the terms have their usual significance. These data have been examined in the light of Masson's equation:

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 + a\sqrt{C},$$

as the plot of Φ against $\sqrt{C}$ is linear and the values of Φ_0 and the constant 'a' could be calculated from the intercept and slope, respectively. These values are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent composition.	KCl		NaCl		$\Delta\Phi_0$.
	Φ_0 .	a.	Φ_0 .	a.	
10%	25.50	1.250	17.00	0.770	8.50
20	24.00	0.812	12.50	1.440	11.50
30	21.25	1.000	12.50	1.200	8.75

Scott *et al.*² attribute to Φ_0 , the apparent molal volume at zero concentration, an additive character, depending on the constituent ions of the electrolyte in aqueous solution. The difference in the values of Φ_0 is bound to be connected with the difference in the individual character of the sphere of solvation of the cations and anions and so the value changes with the composition. Hence it is suggested that the number of molecules of each

1. Das and Das, *this Journal*, 1966, 43, 58.

2. *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, *vi*, 8, 218.

3. Harned and Owen, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions".

species constituting the sphere of solvation depends not only on the character of the ion but also on the specific properties of both kinds of molecules present in the solvent. In a pair of electrolytes like KCl—NaCl, the additive character of Φ_0 from medium to medium can be expected only when the sphere of solvation of K^+ and Na^+ are equally affected. If one of these ions shows any preferential behaviour for one type of molecules present in the solvent, the alteration in the composition of the solvent would necessarily exhibit this preferential behaviour or in other words, the solvation sphere of the two ions will not only differ in composition but also in character. Therefore the additive character of Φ_0 will not be exhibited. Table I shows that the difference in the value of Φ_0 ($\Delta\Phi_0$) is not the same for the pair of electrolytes KCl—NaCl. This departure is attributed to the essential difference between solvation sphere of K^+ and Na^+ at different solvent compositions.

The constant 'a' in Masson's equation is associated with interionic properties and can be calculated from the known physical constants and should be theoretically the same for the same valency type. Table I also shows that the constant 'a' for KCl and for NaCl is not same. Further investigations in this line are in progress.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK-3.